

SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELLS AND SELF-EFFICACY IN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF STA. CRUZ NORTH, DAVAO DEL SUR

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Abstract. The study assessed the relationship between School Learning Action Cells Implementation Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students in Sta Cruz North District, Davao del Sur Schools Division. This used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher-respondents. The treatments used were Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of school learning action cells implementation which content and pedagogy, learner diversity and student inclusion, curriculum context, localization and indigenization, assessment and reporting, and ICT integration in instruction and assessment are sometimes manifested, the extent of self-efficacy in junior high school students of which problem-solving confidence and persistence are oftentimes manifested; while performance expectations and task-specific confidence are sometimes manifested. There is a significant relationship between school learning action cells and self-efficacy in junior high school students. All domains of School Learning Action Cells implementation significantly influenced self-efficacy in junior high school students. Future research may investigate the scalability of successful practices in different educational contexts.

KEY WORDS

1. School learning action cell.
2. Self-Efficacy.
3. Junior High School Sta Cruz North, Davao del Sur.

1. Introduction

School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) have gained traction internationally as an innovative educational approach, reflecting a growing trend towards collaborative and student-centered learning. One notable trend is the widespread recognition of the importance of student agency and peer learning. Internationally, educators increasingly acknowledge the value of involving students in the decision-making processes regarding their education. SLACs provide a structured platform for students to actively participate in shaping their learning experiences. Another trend is the emphasis on fostering 21st-century skills. SLACs often incorporate project-based learning, critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills into their activities.

The international landscape strongly emphasizes inclusivity and diversity within learning action cells. Educators increasingly recognize the importance of tailoring educational approaches to meet the needs of diverse student

populations, including those with various learning styles, abilities, and cultural backgrounds. SLACs are seen as adaptable and inclusive environments catering to these diverse needs. Technology integration is another prevailing trend. Many SLACs leverage digital tools and online platforms to facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing, enabling students worldwide to connect and learn. This aligns with the global push for digital literacy and technology integration in education. Additionally, there's a growing recognition of the role of SLACs in promoting sustainable development and global citizenship. These cells often emphasize real-world problem-solving and encourage students to engage with international issues, fostering a sense of responsibility towards their communities and the planet (López-Crespo, Saida and Gairín Sallán, 2023). Australian universities are places of incredible diversity, and there is broad acceptance that promoting and learning through diversity can enhance all students' university experiences. However, there needs to be more information about how this is done across the Australian higher education sector. Baker (2022) presents diversity strategies, inclusion policies, and public-facing websites. The author believed that engaging with diversity and diverse ideas is essential to their learning experiences but that many barriers to inclusive engagement remain. More must be done to ensure that engagement with diverse people and ideas is facilitated effectively, comprehensively, and often on Australian university campuses. Kelly et.al. (2022) conceptualize outdoor learning, highlighting the potential for more child-initiated experiential learning. The diverse profile of children in primary schools calls on teachers to prepare teaching, learning, and assessment activities to address a wide range of social, emotional, physical, cognitive, and cultural needs. He recognizes outdoor learning as an effective pedagogy to promote inclusion and reduce the barriers to full participation in the primary classroom. Implementing

School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) in the Philippines faces several challenges unique to the local educational context. One significant challenge is resource constraints. Many schools in the Philippines need more resources, such as textbooks, technology, and basic classroom materials. This scarcity can hinder the effective implementation of SLACs, which often require access to various learning resources and tools. Another issue is teacher capacity and professional development. While SLACs encourage collaborative learning and innovative teaching methods, not all teachers may be adequately prepared to facilitate these activities. Ongoing professional development and training are essential to equip educators with the skills and knowledge to guide students effectively within SLACs (Villanueva et.al., 2022). Infrastructure and connectivity pose additional challenges. In many regions of the Philippines, there are issues with inadequate physical infrastructure and limited internet connectivity, especially in rural areas. Ensuring that SLACs are inclusive and accessible to all students while catering to their individual needs requires careful planning and support. Cultural and regional diversity also plays a role. The Philippines is a culturally diverse country with multiple languages and dialects spoken across its regions. Adapting SLACs to accommodate these linguistic and cultural differences can be complex, requiring sensitivity to local contexts. Lastly, the bureaucratic challenges in the Philippine education system can impact the adoption and sustainability of SLACs. Shifting from traditional teaching methods to more student-centered approaches can be met with resistance, and navigating administrative processes to implement changes at the institutional level can take time and effort. In addressing these challenges, education stakeholders in the Philippines must collaborate, invest in teacher training and development, advocate for increased resources, and tailor SLACs to the specific needs of local communities. Overcom-

ing these hurdles can unlock the potential of SLACs to provide meaningful and compelling learning experiences for Filipino students (Vil-lanueva and Ortega-Dela Cruz, (2022). Thus, in the locality of the schools, implementing the policies from the Department of Education fully supports the continuing professional development of its training personnel based on the principle of lifelong learning and commitment to developing teachers' potential for success. This can be done through the School-based LAC, which primarily functions as a potential learning community for teachers to help them improve practice and learner achievement (DO 35, S 2016).

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps in the conduct of the study. This includes the selection of the study's design, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical consideration, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are essential to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The researcher used artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work throughout preparation. Artificial Intelligence was specifically used to improve the manuscript's overall quality, coherence, and correctness. This procedure is being made clear in order to uphold ethical norms in research and preserve transparency. Using AI for proofreading shows a dedication to using cutting-edge technologies responsibly and recognizes the growing use and potential of AI in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is a comprehensive approach in the field of research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and predict outcomes in a systematic manner. This design typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervention, manipulation, or control of variables (Creswel, 2014). The study examining the impact of School Learning Action Cells (SLACs) on Mathematics Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students employs a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design to gain a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between SLAC participation and mathematics self-efficacy among students. This research design involves collecting data without manipulating any variables or introducing interventions intentionally, aligning with the natural setting of SLAC implementation in schools. Descriptive-correlational methods allow researchers to describe the current state of SLACs, gather data on students' self-efficacy beliefs, and investigate potential associations between these variables. By collecting data through surveys, observations, or interviews, researchers can describe the characteristics of SLACs, identify patterns of participation, and measure students' self-efficacy levels. Additionally, the design's predictive aspect permits researchers to explore whether certain variables within SLACs, such as frequency of participation or specific collaborative activities, can predict changes or improvements in mathematics self-efficacy among junior high school students. This approach provides insights into the current state of SLACs and their potential impact. It informs educators and policymakers about effective strategies to enhance students' self-efficacy within the existing school framework.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Secondary School Teachers in Sta Cruz North District, Davao del Sur Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 80 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each respective School. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were selected for they were assumed to have been engaged in the implementation of the school learning action cell as DepED policy DO 35 S 2016. They are qualified for they were expected to have performed and contributed given that they have attended various activities about the school's management in curriculum delivery and implementation. This is done through school faculty meetings for the betterment of the school and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health

Meanwhile, to determine the extent Mathematics Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Stu-

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explain the data gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The state-

protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of School Learning Action Cells in terms of learner diversity and student inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, ICT integration in instruction and assessment, and curriculum context, localization, and indigenization. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the Self-efficacy in Junior High School Students in terms of performance expectations, persistence, task-specific confidence, and problem-solving confidence. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.895, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of School Learning Action Cells sessions. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Students, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

ments are based on the policies and guidelines of the College where the researcher is studying, especially in the current full face-to-face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. On the

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The School Learning Action Cells sessions is always manifested
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The School Learning Action Cells sessions is oftentimes manifested
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The School Learning Action Cells sessions is sometimes manifested
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The School Learning Action Cells sessions is rarely manifested
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The School Learning Action Cells sessions is not manifested

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1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The Self-Efficacy of students not manifested

second week of October 2023, the researcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004). On the last week of January up to the first week of February 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao del Sur, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study among the Sta Cruz North District. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents

who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometimes on the first week of June 2024, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of School Learning Action Cells implementation and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of self-efficacy in Junior High School Students. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells imple-

mentation and Mathematics self-efficacy in Junior High School Students. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the School Learning Action Cells implementation indicators that significantly influence self-efficacy in Junior High School Students (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the responses from the data gathered in tabular and textual form. It includes discussions of the results based on an integration with reviews of the related studies. This will be the basis for the decisions to be made given the hypothesis posed.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of school learning action cells implementation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: content and pedagogy (3.39), learner diversity and student inclusion (3.34), curriculum context, localization and indigenization (3.34), assessment and reporting (3.25) and ICT integration in instruction and assessment (2.79) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.22 denotes the extent of school learning action cell implementation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of School Learning Action Cells Implementation

No	School Learning Action Cells Implementation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion	3.34	Moderately Extensive
2	Content and Pedagogy	3.39	Moderately Extensive
3	Assessment and Reporting	3.25	Moderately Extensive
4	ICT Integration in Instruction and Assessment	2.79	Moderately Extensive
5	Curriculum Context, Localization and Indigenization	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.22	Moderately Extensive

The extent of School Learning Action Cells implementation is a critical measure of their impact on educational practices within a school. These cells represent collaborative spaces where educators come together to share insights, discuss challenges, and collectively work towards improving teaching and learning. The successful implementation of these cells can be gauged by their integration into the school's culture and the extent to which they influence instructional methods, professional development, and overall school improvement initiatives. Key indicators of successful implementation include active participation of educators, the regularity of meetings, and the incorporation of data-driven decision-making processes (Bayran, 2022). The cells' effectiveness may also be evident in the positive changes observed in student outcomes, reflecting the impact of collaborative efforts on teaching strategies and student engagement. Additionally, the extent to which the cells contribute to a culture of continuous improvement and innovation within the school is crucial in assessing their implementation. Monitoring how the insights generated within these cells translate into actionable changes in curriculum, assessment, and classroom practices provides a tangible measure of their effectiveness in fostering a dynamic and responsive learning environment (Istiningsih, 2022).

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: problem-solving confidence (3.59) and persistence (3.55) are oftentimes manifested; while, performance expectations (3.15) and task-specific confidence (3.11) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.35 denotes the extent of school learning action cell implementation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: problem-solving confidence (3.59) and persistence (3.55) are oftentimes manifested; while, performance expectations (3.15) and task-specific confidence (3.11) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.35 denotes the extent of school learning action cell implementation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students

No	Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Performance Expectations	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Persistence	3.55	Extensive
3	Task-Specific Confidence	3.11	Moderately Extensive
4	Problem-Solving Confidence	3.59	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.35	Moderately Extensive

Shimizu (2022) revealed that Mathematics self-efficacy refers to students’ beliefs in their ability to understand and succeed in mathematical tasks. Successful implementation is evident in the degree to which students exhibit confidence in their mathematical abilities, approach problem-solving with a positive mindset, and persist in the face of challenges. A high level of mathematics self-efficacy is associated with proactive engagement in classroom activities, a willingness to tackle complex problems, and a positive attitude towards learning mathematics. On the contrary, lower self-efficacy may result in hesitancy, anxiety, and a reluctance to participate in math-related activities. Ames-Guerrero (2023) proposed that teachers and educators play a crucial role in fostering mathematics self-efficacy by employing teaching strategies that build students’ confidence, providing positive reinforcement, and creating a supportive learning environment. Regular assessments and observations of students’ attitudes, participation, and problem-solving approaches can

offer insights into the extent of mathematics self-efficacy, guiding educators in tailoring interventions to enhance students’ confidence and overall mathematical proficiency in the junior high school years.

Relationship between School Learning Action Cells Implementation and Mathematics Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students

Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells implementation and mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells implementation and mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significantly strong positive correlation between School Learning Action Cells implementation ($r=0.879$; $p<.002$) and self-efficacy in junior high school students.

Table 3. Relationship between School Learning Action Cells Implementation and Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students

Variables	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
School Learning Action Cells Implementation				
Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students	0.879	<0.002	Significant	Reject H_0

The significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells (SLAC) implementation and mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students highlights the potential impact of collaborative learning environments on students' confidence and proficiency in mathematics. When SLACs are effectively implemented, they provide a platform for educators to address challenges and share strategies to enhance teaching methods collectively. This collaborative approach can positively influence the learning experiences of junior high school students, particularly in mathematics (Shimizu, 2022). As educators collaboratively explore and implement innovative instructional practices within SLACs, students may benefit from diverse teaching strategies that cater to various learning styles and needs. This tailored and inclusive approach contributes to building students' mathematics self-efficacy by fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment. The open exchange of ideas within SLACs can also lead to identifying and implementing effective interventions that boost students' confidence in

tackling mathematical challenges. The relationship between SLAC implementation and mathematics self-efficacy underscores the importance of collective efforts in shaping a positive and empowering educational experience for junior high school students, specifically in the realm of mathematics education.

Domains of School Learning Action Cells implementation significantly influence self-efficacy in junior high school students

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis showing that the implementation of School Learning Action Cells significantly influences mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. Indicators of School Learning Action Cells implementation in terms of learner diversity and student inclusion (0.000), content and pedagogy (0.002), assessment and reporting (0.000), ICT integration in instruction and assessment (0.001) and curriculum context, localization and indigenization (0.001) significantly influence mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Indicators of School Learning Action Cells Implementation Significantly Influence Self-Efficacy in Junior High School Students

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	Interpretation
(Intercept)	4.145		0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
(Intercept)	0.313		0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
learner diversity and student inclusion	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315	0.000
*Reject H_0						
content and pedagogy	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196	0.002
*Reject H_0						
assessment and reporting	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038	0.000
*Reject H_0						
ict integration in instruction and assessment	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196	0.001
*Reject H_0						
curriculum context, localization and indigenization	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654	0.001	0.001
*Reject H_0						
$R^2 = 0.866$						
$F\text{-value} = 264.597$						
$p\text{-value} = < 0.001$						

Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.866 suggests that the indicators of School Learning Action Cells implementation, can be explained by 86.6%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (264.597) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. The successful implementation of School Learning Action Cells (SLAC) significantly influences mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students through several key indicators. Firstly, learner diversity and student inclusion within SLAC foster a supportive environment that recognizes and accommodates the diverse backgrounds, learning styles, and abilities of students. This inclusivity contributes to a sense of belonging, positively impacting students' self-efficacy in mathematics. Secondly, the focus on content and pedagogy within SLAC allows educators to collaboratively explore and implement effective teaching strategies that cater to varied learning needs. By tailoring instruction to diverse student profiles, SLAC can enhance students' understanding and confidence in mathematical concepts (Chan, et.al., 2022). Thirdly, assessment and reporting practices within SLAC can provide targeted feedback, recognizing individual progress and ad-

ressing specific challenges. This formative assessment approach positively influences students' self-perception and efficacy in their mathematical abilities. Fourthly, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in SLAC enhances instructional methods and assessment practices, creating a dynamic and engaging learning environment. The utilization of digital tools aligns with contemporary learning preferences, potentially boosting students' confidence in navigating mathematical challenges in a technology-driven era. Lastly, the emphasis on curriculum context, localization, and indigenization within SLAC ensures that the mathematics curriculum aligns with the cultural backgrounds and contexts of the students, making the learning experience more relevant and meaningful (Sharma, et.al., 2019). This alignment contributes to students' sense of ownership and pride in their mathematical abilities, positively impacting their self-efficacy. In summary, the successful implementation of SLAC, as evidenced by attention to learner diversity, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, ICT integration, and curriculum context, localization, and indigenization, collectively influences junior high school students' self-efficacy by fostering an inclusive, dynamic, and culturally relevant learning environment (Ames-Guerrero, 2023).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations are delineated in accordance with the analyzed and discussed data, along with the implications drawn from the findings. The findings emanate from the articulated statement of the problem, while the conclusions are derived from the resultant findings. The recommendations, in turn, are formulated based on the implications gleaned from the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The extent of school learning action cells implementation in content and pedagogy, learner diversity and student inclusion, curriculum context, localization and indig-

enization, assessment and reporting, and ICT integration in instruction and assessment is sometimes manifested. The overall mean denotes that the implementation is sometimes manifested,

thus moderately extensive. The self-efficacy in junior high school students of which problem-solving confidence and persistence are oftentimes manifested, while performance expectations and task-specific confidence (are sometimes manifested. The overall mean denotes the extent of self-efficacy sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between School Learning Action Cells implementation and self-efficacy in junior high school students. All the Domains of School Learning Action Cells implementation in terms of learner diversity and student inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, ICT integration in instruction and assessment and curriculum context, localization, and indigenization significantly influence self-efficacy in junior high school students.

Conclusions

Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions: The extent of school learning action cell implementation, which includes content and pedagogy, learner diversity and student inclusion, curriculum context, localization and indigenization, assessment and reporting, and ICT integration in instruction and assessment, is sometimes manifested. The extent of self-efficacy in junior high school students of which problem-solving confidence and persistence are oftentimes manifested, while performance expectations and task-specific confidence are sometimes manifested. There is a significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells implementation and self-efficacy in junior high school students. Implementation of all the Domains of School Learning Action Cells in terms of learner diversity and student inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, ICT integration in instruction and assessment and curriculum context, and localization and indigenization significantly influence mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. Al-

bert Bandura's theory of self-efficacy is highly relevant to the application of junior high school students' performance in mathematics. This theory posits that individuals' beliefs in their capabilities significantly influence their behavior, motivation, and, ultimately, their success. In the context of junior high school students learning mathematics, self-efficacy plays a crucial role. Students with high mathematics self-efficacy believe they can understand complex mathematical concepts, solve challenging problems, and excel in the subject. These beliefs foster greater motivation to engage with mathematics, leading to increased effort and persistence in facing difficulties. They are more likely to set ambitious goals and confidently approach mathematical tasks, which can result in improved academic performance. Conversely, students with low mathematics self-efficacy may avoid math-related challenges and become discouraged more efficiently, potentially hindering their mathematical development. Educators should strive to enhance students' confidence in their mathematical abilities. This can be achieved by providing opportunities for success, offering constructive feedback, and creating a supportive learning environment. Teachers can encourage students to set achievable goals, monitor their progress, and celebrate their accomplishments, reinforcing their self-belief. Additionally, showcasing real-world applications of mathematics can help students understand the practical relevance of the subject, further boosting their self-efficacy.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions: The extent of school learning action cell implementation, which includes content and pedagogy, learner diversity and student inclusion, curriculum context, localization and indigenization, assessment and reporting, and ICT integration in instruction and assessment, is sometimes manifested. The extent of self-efficacy in junior high school students of which problem-

solving confidence and persistence are often-times manifested, while performance expectations and task-specific confidence are sometimes manifested. There is a significant relationship between School Learning Action Cells implementation and self-efficacy in junior high school students. Implementation of all the Domains of School Learning Action Cells in terms of learner diversity and student inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, ICT integration in instruction and assessment and curriculum context, and localization and indigenization significantly influence mathematics self-efficacy in junior high school students. Albert Bandura's theory of self-efficacy is highly relevant to the application of junior high school students' performance in mathematics. This theory posits that individuals' beliefs in their capabilities significantly influence their behavior, motivation, and, ultimately, their success. In the context of junior high school students learning mathematics, self-efficacy plays a crucial role. Students with high mathematics self-efficacy believe they can understand complex mathematical concepts, solve challenging problems, and excel in the subject. These beliefs foster greater motivation to engage with mathematics, leading to increased effort and persistence in facing difficulties. They are more likely to set ambitious goals and confidently approach mathematical tasks, which can result in improved academic performance. Conversely, students with low mathematics self-efficacy may avoid math-related challenges and become discouraged more efficiently, potentially hindering their mathematical development. Educators should strive to enhance students' confidence in their mathematical abilities. This can be achieved by providing opportunities for success, offering constructive feedback, and creating a supportive learning environment. Teachers can encourage students

to set achievable goals, monitor their progress, and celebrate their accomplishments, reinforcing their self-belief. Additionally, showcasing real-world applications of mathematics can help students understand the practical relevance of the subject, further boosting their self-efficacy.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; The Public School District Supervisor may provide support and resources for ongoing professional development programs that focus on collaborative teaching methods and the integration of inclusive practices within SLAC. Additionally, fostering a culture that values and prioritizes students' diversity will contribute to a more inclusive learning environment. School Principal. Facilitate and encourage teachers' active participation in SLAC, ensuring that these collaborative platforms become integral to the school's professional development initiatives. Provide leadership that fosters a culture of continuous improvement, innovation, and inclusivity, which will contribute to the success of SLAC. Teacher. may embrace the collaborative opportunities presented by SLAC, actively engaging in the sharing of best practices, strategies, and experiences. Implementing differentiated instructional methods, leveraging technology, and embracing culturally responsive teaching approaches will contribute to enhancing students' mathematics self-efficacy. Future Researcher. Longitudinal studies may be conducted to assess the sustained impact of SLAC on mathematics self-efficacy. Investigating the scalability of successful practices, exploring additional factors influencing self-efficacy, and examining the transferability of findings to different educational contexts will further enrich the understanding of collaborative learning initiatives like SLAC.

5. References

- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- A'mar, Fadia; Eleyan, Derar (2022). Effect of Principal's Technology Leadership on Teacher's Technology Integration *International Journal of Instruction*, v15 n1 p781-798 Jan 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=ICT+Integration+in+Instruction+and+Assessment++as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1331162>
- Antoninis, Manos; April, Daniel; Barakat, Bilal; Bella, Nicole; D'Addio, Anna Cristina; Eck, Matthias; Endrizzi, Francesca; Joshi, Priyadarshani; Kubacka, Katarzyna; McWilliam, Alasdair; Murakami, Yuki; Smith, Will; Stipanovic, Laura; Vidarte, Rosa; Zekrya, Lema (2020). All Means All: An Introduction to the "2020 Global Education Monitoring Report" on Inclusion *Prospects: Quarterly Review of Comparative Education*, v49 n3-4 p103-109 Nov 2020
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09505-x>
- Appiah, Joseph Bekoe; Korkor, Sarah; Arthur, Yarhands Dissou; Obeng, Benjamin Adu (2022). Mathematics Achievement in High Schools, the Role of the Teacher-Student Relationship, Students' Self-Efficacy, and Students' Perception of Mathematics *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, v17 n3 Article em0688 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Performance+Expectations+as+indicator+of+Mathematics+Self-Efficacy+in+Junior+High+School+Students&id=EJ1357964>
- Archambault, Leanna; Leary, Heather; Rice, Kerry (2022). Pillars of Online Pedagogy: A Framework for Teaching in Online Learning Environments *Educational Psychologist*, v57 n3 p178-191 2022
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2022.2051513>
- Ames-Guerrero, Rita J.; Huamani-Cahua, Julio C.; Sato-Ruiz, Jorge E.; Panduro-Tenazoa, Nadia M.; Zegarra-Valdivia, Jonathan A. (2023). Self-Efficacy and Problem Solving as Predictors of Attitudes toward Research: A Study with University Students of Amazonia in Virtual Education 2021 *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, v21 n59 p103-124 2023
<https://ojs.ual.es/ojs/index.php/EJREP/article/view/7152/7722>
- Aslam, Rabia; Khan, Najmonnisa; Ahmed, Ushaque (2020). Technology Integration and Teachers' Professional Knowledge with Reference to International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE)-Standard: A Causal Study *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, v7 n2 p307-327 Dec 2020
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=ICT+Integration+in+Instruction+and+Assessment++as+co>

- Athira, B. K.; Rajendran, Poornima (2023). The Social Principle of Inclusive Education and Addressing Diversity in Indian Schools: An Appraisal of Post-Salamanca Initiatives in India *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, v11 n2 p92-99 Mar 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learner+Diversity+and+Inclusion+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1380190>
- Bahn, Constance Marie (2022). Teachers' Perspectives Implementing Inquiry-Based Learning in the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Program *ProQuest LLC*, Ph.D. Dissertation, Walden University <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Curriculum+Contextualization%2c+Localization+and+Indigenization+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED627782>
- Baker, Sally; Kim, Hyejeong; Marangell, Samantha; Baik, Chi; Arkoudis, Sophie; Croucher, Gwilym; Laffernis, Farhana (2022). Engaging 'Diverse' Students: An Audit of Strategies to Foster Intercultural Engagement in Australian Public Universities. Project Report *Melbourne Centre for the Study of Higher Education* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learner+Diversity+and+Inclusion+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED624242>
- Bayrak, Fatma (2022). Investigation of the Web-Based Self-Assessment System Based on Assessment Analytics in Terms of Perceived Self-Intervention *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, v27 n3 p639-662 Sep 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10758-021-09511-8>
- Byukusenge, Céline; Nsanganwimana, Florian; Tarmo, Albert Paulo (2023). Enhancing Students' Understanding of Nerve Cells' Structures and Their Symbiotic Functioning by Using Technology-Enhanced Instruction Incorporating Virtual Labs and Animations *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, v32 n1 p13-25 Feb 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10956-022-10002-3>
- Capuno, Reylan; Necesario, Renante; Etcuban, Jonathan Olores; Espina, Raymond; Padillo, Gengen; Manguilimotan, Ramil (2019). Attitudes, Study Habits, and Academic Performance of Junior High School Students in Mathematics *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, v14 n3 p547-561 2019
- Chan, Jenny Yun-Chen; Ottmar, Erin R.; Lee, Ji-Eun (2022). Slow Down to Speed Up: Longer Pause Time before Solving Problems Relates to Higher Strategy Efficiency *Grantee Submission* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2021.102109>

- Doucette, Danny; Daane, Abigail R.; Flynn, Angela; Gosling, Chris; Hsi, Dana; Mathis, Clausell; Morrison, Andrew; Park, Shinae; Rifkin, Moses; Tabora, Johan (2022). Teaching Equity in Chemistry *Journal of Chemical Education*, v99 n1 p301-306 Jan 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.1c00415>
- Driscoll, Kerry; Cheeseman, Jill (2022). School Mathematics Leaders' Support of Primary Teachers' Professional Learning in Meetings *Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia*, Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia (MERGA) (44th, Launceston, Tasmania, Australia, Jul 3-7, 2022) <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Content+and+Pedagogy++as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED623808>
- Filipkowski, Craig (2023). School Leader Development with Action Learning *Action Learning: Research and Practice*, v20 n1 p17-37 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14767333.2022.2086532>
- Gao, Jie (2020). Sources of Mathematics Self-Efficacy in Chinese Students: A Mixed-Method Study with Q-Sorting Procedure *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, v18 n4 p713-732 Apr 2020 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10763-019-09984-1>
- Gujarati, D.N. and Porter, D.C. (2009) Basic Econometrics. 5th Edition, McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, 400.
- Hannah, Darren; Sinnema, Claire; Robinson, Viviane (2022). Understanding Curricula as Theories of Action *Curriculum Journal*, v33 n3 p362-377 Sep 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/curj.138>
- Istiningsih, Istiningsih (2022). Impact of ICT Integration on the Development of Vocational High School Teacher TPACK in the Digital Age 4.0 *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues*, v14 n1 p103-116 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=ICT+Integration+in+Instruction+and+Assessment++as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1334627>
- Javier, Babylyn F. (2021). Practices of Filipino Public High School Teachers on Digital Teaching and Learning Technologies during the COVID-19 Pandemic Basis for Learning Action Cell Sessions *Online Submission* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED616121>

- Kalykbayeva, Almagul; Autayeva, Akbota; Orazayeva, Gulzhan; Kassymzhanova, Gulnar; Zhigitbekova, Bakyt; Bekmuratova, Gulzhanar (2022). The Attitude of Teachers toward Students' Self-Assessment of Educational Achievements in Inclusive Education Lessons *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, v17 n2 p643-651 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Assessment+and+Reporting+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1331883>
- Kelly, Orla; Buckley, Karen; Lieberman, Lauren J.; Arndt, Katrina (2022). Universal Design for Learning -- A Framework for Inclusion in Outdoor Learning *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education*, v25 n1 p75-89 Apr 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s42322-022-00096-z>
- Keohane, Alexandra Marie (2022) . Implementation of Social-Emotional Curriculum Terminology in Elementary Schools *ProQuest LLC*, Ed.D. Dissertation, Northeastern University <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Curriculum+Contextualization%2c+Localization+and+Indigenization+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&pg=2&id=ED630274>
- Khoza, Simon Bheki; Biyela, Audrey Thabile (2020). Decolonising Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of First Year Mathematics Students *Education and Information Technologies*, v25 n4 p2665-2679 Jul 2020 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-10084-4>
- Klee, Holly L.; Miller, Angela D.; Buehl, Michelle M. (2023). Mathematics Anxiety, Self-Concept, and Self-Efficacy: A Multidimensional Scaling Consideration of Measures. *Journal of Experimental Education*, v91 n3 p494-516 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00220973.2021.2024788>
- Kundu, Arnab; Bej, Tripti (2021). Ingestion and Integration of ICTs for Pedagogy in Indian Private High Schools *E-Learning and Digital Media*, v18 n2 p163-184 Mar 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2042753020957493>
- Kyaruzi, Florence (2023). Impact of Gender on Sources of Students' Self-Efficacy in Mathematics in Tanzanian Secondary Schools *International Journal of School & Educational Psychology*, v11 n1 p72-85 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/21683603.2021.1945512>
- López-Crespo, Saida; Gairín Sallán, Joaquín (2023). School Principals' Actions to Promote Informal Learning among Teaching Staff *Teacher Development*, v27 n3 p297-313 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2023.2191984>

- Luo, Feiya; Ijeluola, Stephen Abiodun; Westerlund, Jill; Walker, Amanda; Denham, André; Walker, John; Young, Cherelle (2023). Supporting Elementary Teachers' Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge in Computational Thinking Integration *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, v32 n4 p583-596 Aug 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10956-023-10045-0>
- Meta-Assessment of the Assessment Culture: Using a Formal Review to Guide Improvement in Assessment Practices and Document Progress *Research & Practice in Assessment*, v16 n2 p33-45 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Assessment+and+Reporting+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1348820>
- Mori, Kazuo; Kudo, Hiroshi (2022). I Can Do It Well Because I Did It Well: The Effect of Promoted Self-Efficacy through Induced Success Performance in Junior High School Students *Contemporary School Psychology*, v26 n3 p321-327 Sep 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40688-021-00367-4>
- Mukuka, Angel; Mutarutinya, Védaste; Balimuttajjo, Sudi (2021). Mediating Effect of Self-Efficacy on the Relationship between Instruction and Students' Mathematical Reasoning *Journal on Mathematics Education*, v12 n1 p73-92 Jan 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Task-Specific+Confidence+as+indicator+of+Mathematics+Self-Efficacy+in+Junior+High+School+Students&pg=2&id=EJ1294665>
- Museus, Samuel D.; Williams, Michael Steven; Lourdes, Alexandra (2022). Analyzing the Relationship between Campus Environments and Academic Self-Efficacy in College *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, v59 n5 p487-501 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/19496591.2021.1967759>
- Norton, Stephen (2019). Middle School Mathematics Pre-Service Teachers' Content Knowledge, Confidence and Self-Efficacy *Teacher Development*, v23 n5 p529-548 2019 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2019.1668840>
- Özeren, Seçil; Top, Ercan (2023). The Effects of Augmented Reality Applications on the Academic Achievement and Motivation of Secondary School Students *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, v11 n1 p25-40 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1376331>
- Özcan, Bahadır; Kültür, Yusuf Ziya (2021). The Relationship between Sources of Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Mathematics Test and Course Achievement in High School Seniors *SAGE Open*, v11 n3 Jul-Sep 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/21582440211040124>

- Pallant, J. (2020). *SPSS Survival Manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS (7th ed.)*. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003117452>
- Palieraki, Stefania; Koutrouba, Konstantina (2021). Differentiated Instruction in Information and Communications Technology Teaching and Effective Learning in Primary Education *European Journal of Educational Research*, v10 n3 p1487-1503 2021
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=ICT+Integration+in+Instruction+and+Assessment++as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1307442>
- Qi, Wenhui; Qin, Yuyou; Sang, Guoyuan; Wang, Ning (2023). Family Functioning and Learning Engagement of Junior High School Students in Rural China: The Mediating Effect of Academic Self-Efficacy *Educational Psychology*, v43 n2-3 p137-154 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2023.2190067>
- Quinlan, Catherine L.; Picho, Katherine; Burke, Janelle (2022). Creating an Instrument to Measure Social and Cultural Self-Efficacy Indicators for Persistence of HBCU Undergraduates in STEM *Research in Science Education*, v52 n5 p1583-1601 Oct 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11165-021-09992-8>
- Reinking, Anni K.; Thigpen, Laycee (2022). Coaching for Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Accessibility, and Belonging in Early Childhood: A Step-by-Step Guide for Programs and Schools *Brookes Publishing Company*
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learner+Diversity+and+Inclusion+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED627960>
- Rhodes, Kate; Calder, Nigel (2022). Teachers Implementing New Primary School Digital Technology Areas: What Are We Teaching Now? *Waikato Journal of Education*, v27 n3 p159-173 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Curriculum+Contextualization%2c+Localization+and+Indigenization+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1374140>
- Sharma, Anu; Pape, Stephen J.; Templin, Jonathan (2019). Testing the Psychometric Properties of the Modeling Self-Efficacy Scale *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, v9 n1 p146-157 2019
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Task-Specific+Confidence+as+indicator+of+Mathematics+Self-Efficacy+in+Junior+High+School+Students&id=EJ1278242>

- Shea, Lynne-Marie; Harkins, Debra; Ray, Sukanya; Grenier, Lauren I. (2023). How Critical Is Service-Learning Implementation? *Journal of Experiential Education*, v46 n2 p197-214 Jun 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/10538259221122738>
- Shimizu, Yuno (2022). Relation between Mathematical Proof Problem Solving, Math Anxiety, Self-Efficacy, Learning Engagement, and Backward Reasoning *Journal of Education and Learning*, v11 n6 p62-75 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Problem-solving+Confidence+as+indicator+of+Mathematics+Self-Efficacy+in+Junior+High+School+Students&id=EJ1372466>
- Smale, William T.; Hutcheson, Ryan; Russo, Charles J. (2021). Cell Phones, Student Rights, and School Safety: Finding the Right Balance *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, n195 p49-64 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=EJ1287931>
- Sutama; Anif, Sofyan; Prayitno, Harun Joko; Narimo, Sabar; Fuadi, Djalal; Sari, Diana Purwita; Adnan, Mazlini (2021). Metacognition of Junior High School Students in Mathematics Problem Solving Based on Cognitive Style *Asian Journal of University Education*, v17 n1 p134-144 Jan 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Problem-solving+Confidence+as+indicator+of+Mathematics+Self-Efficacy+in+Junior+High+School+Students&id=EJ1291287>
- Tay, H. Y.; Tan, K. H. K.; Deneen, C. C.; Leong, W. S.; Fulmer, Gavin W.; Brown, Gavin T. L. (2020). Middle Leaders' Perceptions and Actions on Assessment: The Technical, Tactical and Ethical *School Leadership & Management*, v40 n1 p45-63 2020 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2019.1582016>
- Villanueva, Jonathan S.; Ortega-Dela Cruz, Ruth A. (2022). Confronting Challenges of School-Based Management in a Developing Country *Journal on School Educational Technology*, v17 n3 p44-55 Dec 2021-Feb 2022 <https://doi.org/10.26634/jsch.17.3.18645>
- Watt, Michael (2020). The National School Reform Agreement: Its Implications for State-Level Curriculum Reforms *Online Submission* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Curriculum+Contextualization%2c+Localization+and+Indigenization+as+a+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&id=ED604410>

- Wen, Yun; Gwendoline, Choon Lang Quek; Lau, Sin Yee (2021). ICT-Supported Home-Based Learning in K-12: A Systematic Review of Research and Implementation *TechTrends: Linking Research and Practice to Improve Learning*, v65 n3 p371-378 May 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11528-020-00570-9>
- Yang, Edith; Halpin, Peter; Handy, Daniel (2022). Using Psychometric Analysis to Improve Soft-Skill Assessments *MDRC* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Assessment+and+Reporting+as+component+of+School+Learning+Action+Cell+implementation+&pg=4&id=ED624221>
- Zhu, Yan; Kaiser, Gabriele (2022). Impacts of Classroom Teaching Practices on Students' Mathematics Learning Interest, Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Mathematics Test Achievements: A Secondary Analysis of Shanghai Data from the International Video Study Global Teaching InSights *ZDM: Mathematics Education*, v54 n3 p581-593 Jun 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01343-9>